

An Analysis towards Teachers' Perception on their Schools' Conduciveness to English Language Learners' Success at SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate

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Abstract

This study aims at the perception of English teachers on the influence of the conducive environment of the school on students' English learning achievement (SMA Negeri 3 Ternate City, Indonesia). By involving two English teachers at the school, researchers conducted interviews to obtain the required information. By using content analysis, researchers find a variety of very interesting information to pay attention to. In fact, the level of environmental conduciveness in the school also affects the level of achievement of English learning. The contributing factors are differences in students' linguistic backgrounds, lack of technology support, and low time allocation for English subjects. Researchers also found that differences in culture, race, and religion did not affect the conduciveness of the English learning environment at all so that these variables were not relevant to student learning outcomes.

Keywords: *teachers' perception, environment conduciveness, English learning outcomes*

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1. Background

English is now the world's lingua franca and is the language most widely studied in the world, as well as in Indonesia. Based on Permendiknas number 26 of 2006, English began to be taught at the junior high school level. At the level of high school to college, English seems to be an absolute, alongside other subjects English is a foreign language in Indonesia and a local content lesson at school.

Learning in school is very close to the teachers, students, and school environment, how these three greatly affect each other, including the perception of a teacher about students and the environment because it will form their motivation and enthusiasm for learning itself. A teacher must be able to show good attitudes, behaviors, verbal skills when interacting with students, mastering the techniques and procedures for carrying out their assignments in this case teaching and guiding students so that learning objectives are achieved, that is why the teacher's perception is also very important for learning in the classroom and the school environment.

The perception referred to by researchers here is that each different individual has the desire to give meaning and see the same thing in different ways so that they provide different interpretations of what is seen. Successfully supporting and developing ELL requires the cooperation of English teachers.

The same is true of the teacher's perception that the researcher intended. The teacher's perception of the learning environment of students is very important in influencing the learning process. Teacher's perception is an active process that plays a role, not only stimulation about it but also individuals as a whole with their experiences, motivations, and attitudes that are in line in responding to stimuli. How each teacher responds to a condition has something to do with how he/she responds from his/her point of view. That is why researchers want to examine how English teachers in SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate see and interpret their school's conducive conditions for English Language Learners' success. Researchers want to discuss the perception of English teachers of their school's conducive conditions for English language learners' success at their school, namely in SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate.

According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI) Conduciveness is:

“Suatu kondisi yang tidak semrautan dan mendukung untuk terjadinya suatu aktivitas atau tujuan tertentu..”

A previous study examined by Winiger in 2015 discussed the perception of English language educators as ESL in Tennessee and the discussion of schools' conduciveness covering Classroom culture, school climate, school culture, and school partnership. Based on the researchers' pre-observations at SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate, the researchers wanted to specify the current study more about how teachers respond to their perceptions about classroom climate and ELL resilience in SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate with English as a foreign language. When we discuss conduciveness it must lead to the teacher, students, and class atmosphere/class climate. What is the opinion of the teachers in their teaching experience so far in SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate and how the culture of the SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate itself, whether their learning environment is said to be conducive to the success of English language learners. According to Creech (2014) in Degeng, Setyosari, and Dwiyoogo (2016), internal and external conditions of teachers and students can make valuable contributions in building a conducive learning environment.

Validity Teacher's perception of this matter also depends largely on the openness of the teacher to the researcher; in this case, the researcher will be more concerned with the objectives of this study.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Understanding Perception

According to Mulyana in Yazid & Ridwan (2017), perception is an internal process that allows us to choose, organize, and interpret stimuli from our environment and the process that affects us. Meanwhile according to Walgito (2004: 124) in Yazid & Ridwan (2017) perception is a process that is preceded by sensing. Sensing here is a process received from the stimulus by individuals through the receiver. But the process does not stop there, in general, the stimulus is passed on by the nerve to the brain as the center of the nervous system and the next process is a process of perception. Meanwhile, according to Sunaryo (2002: 94) in Yazid & Ridwan (2017), self-perception is essentially due to stimuli originating

from within individuals. In this case, the object is itself, Perception is one's tendency towards something in the relative realm, meaning that the individual's perception of something will vary based on the perception of each person. Perception refers to the way sensory information is organized, interpreted, and consciously experienced. Perception involves bottom-up and top-down processes. One way to think about this concept is that sensation is a physical process, while perception is psychological. So that perception will also affect differences in individual learning outcomes (Nugraha, 2015).

The position of the human senses in the process of perception that is as a tool to interpret the ear, including the human brain is part of the coordination of work systems that support each other so that someone can perceive a thing. Thus the sensing process involves the sensory system and the brain system (the process of thinking/interpretation) which is based on human consciousness so that we can realize our surroundings, including being aware of ourselves. This is in line with Edie (1964) who stated that perception is an original modality of consciousness.

Likewise, the teacher's perception is the result of thinking based on the ability to think that is motivated by various factors in the formation of perception. Researchers, in this case, use the teacher's perception as the main data source to answer the problem formulation. Wagilto (2010) explains the existence of internal and external factors that affect one's perception. Internal factors are factors that exist within the individual themselves, such as roles, experiences, abilities, and terms of reference. While external factors are the stimulus itself and the environment in which the perception takes place.

The process and steps for the perception expressed by Wagilto (2010) are explained by describing:

"The process of perception starts from the natural state (physical process), that is when the object causes a stimulus, and the stimulus is about the sense media. The stimulus received by the sensory organs is then passed on by the sensory nerve to the brain. This process is also called the physiological process. A stimulus that has been received by the brain as a center of consciousness makes individuals aware of what is seen, heard, or touched. The condition of the individual realizing the object received is called a psychological process. Psychological processes are the final stage of the process of perception. From the perceptions created by individuals can respond in various forms. "

Based on the explanation above it can be seen that the process of perception occurs through three stages, namely natural, physiological, and psychological processes. In the process of nature, an object will send stimuli in the form of information that will be captured by the senses and human receptors. Then in the next process, which is the physiological process, not all information will be recorded but there is an effort to select which is the main concern. The information obtained is added or subtracted from what is known and believed from the incomplete to complete so that the process is more active and creative. The results of addition and subtraction produce the results of meanings/meanings that are more regular so that the interpretation phase of an individual is reached.

When interpretation occurs, an understanding of the information obtained is obtained. Although what is not necessarily the same as what is received, but that is the result of perception, is personal between individuals with other individuals as mentioned is influenced by internal and external factors and is limited by the ability of the individual concerned. Perception can be expressed because of feelings, ability to think, individual experiences are

not the same, so in perceiving a stimulus, the results of perception may be different between individuals and other individuals Wagilto (2010).

2.2. School Conduciveness

According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI), Conduciveness is a proper condition supporting activity to achieve a certain goal.

An overview of the classroom atmosphere (classroom climate) stated by Nasution (2003: 119-120) that the learning process should be able to create a class atmosphere or classroom climate that is conducive to supporting the creation of quality learning processes. But unfortunately, the learning process that occurs so far still tends to be one-way. As a result, the learning process that occurs so far has little meaning for students, so it has not been able to develop competencies and potential abilities of students more optimally. An important learning process in schools is not only the material taught or who teaches it, but how it is taught. How the teacher creates a classroom climate in the learning process. Many factors need to be considered in creating a quality and conducive classroom climate to improve student learning achievement. Factors that need to be considered include, namely: first, the learning approach should be oriented to how students learn (student-centered); second, there is teacher appreciation for the active participation of students in each learning context. Third, teachers should be democratic in managing learning activities. Fourth, any problems that arise in the learning process should be discussed dialogically. Fifth, the classroom environment should be set up in such a way as to motivate student learning and encourage the learning process. Sixth, provide various types of learning resources or information related to various learning resources that can be accessed or learned quickly by students.

The learning process is a process of learning interaction between teacher and student and between students and other students. The success or failure of the learning process is influenced by many factors, both factors from the teacher himself, students, supporting facilities, and the atmosphere of the learning interaction process. The class climate is the condition of the classroom environment concerning learning activities. The class climate is an atmosphere marked by the existence of patterns of interaction or communication between teacher-student, student-teacher, and students. The class climate is the condition of the classroom environment concerning learning activities. The class climate is an atmosphere marked by the existence of patterns of interaction or communication between teacher-student, student-teacher, and students.

Meanwhile, A. Sholah (1989: 25-26) who quoted the opinions of Dreikurs and Leron Gray who used a class socio-emotional approach, suggested three types of atmosphere faced by students every day. First, the atmosphere of autocracy: in an atmosphere of autocracy, many teachers apply for orders, use violence, emphasis, competition, punishment, and threats for monitoring student behavior, and the dominant teacher is very prominent. Second, the atmosphere of Laissez-faire: in this atmosphere, the teacher is too little to even show his activities or leadership and gives a lot of freedom to the students. The teacher relinquishes responsibility to group members. And third, a democratic atmosphere: the teacher treats students as individuals who can be responsible, valuable, being able to make decisions, and can solve the problems they face. The impact arising from a democratic atmosphere is the growth of self-confidence, mutual acceptance, and trust in each other, both between teachers and students and between students. The teacher guides develop and share responsibility for all class members including the teacher. Thus this democratic classroom atmosphere will have a positive impact because teachers and students have the opportunity to understand each

other, help, express everything that is felt openly. The teacher will understand the situation of students, and on the other hand, students will see an example and feel some examples can be seen. Related to this matter Sudjana (2002) argues that a democratic learning atmosphere will provide opportunities to achieve optimal learning outcomes, compared to a rigid learning atmosphere, strict discipline with authority on the teacher. Based on some of the explanations and opinions above, it can be concluded that the atmosphere faced by students in learning in schools can be distinguished three types, namely the first autocratic atmosphere with an authoritarian teacher attitude, second, the Laissez-faire atmosphere with the permissive teacher's attitude, and third, the democratic atmosphere with a real teacher attitude. Of the three types of learning atmosphere, a democratic atmosphere with a real teacher's attitude is more likely to provide opportunities in achieving optimal learning outcomes.

2.3. ELL Students' Success Standards

In essence, language including English is a tool for communication between citizens. Communicate means understanding information, thoughts, and feelings. Communication activities are manifested in the act of understanding and expressing nuances of meaning through both the oral and written medium which are influenced, among others, by the situation, people involved in communication, topics, and psychological conditions of people involved in communication. Through language as the main communication tool, mainly through English as a global language, we can develop knowledge, technology, and culture by using that language. In the context of education, this language functions as a communication tool to access, store, and share information. In daily life, it functions as a tool to establish interpersonal relationships, exchanges information, and enjoy the beautiful aspects of the language (see the 2004 English Subject Curriculum).

Based on its function, the objectives of teaching English Subjects in the current Curriculum include: (1) Developing the ability to communicate in the language both oral and written. These abilities include listening (listening), speaking (speaking), reading (reading), and writing (writing); (2) Raising awareness of the nature and importance of English as one of the foreign languages to become the main tool of learning; (3) develop an understanding of the relationship between language and culture and expand cultural horizons. Thus students have cross-cultural insights and involve themselves in cultural diversity.

The formulation of this competency standard in the English Subject Curriculum for SMA and MA as follows:

Communicate verbally and in writing, by using the appropriate variety smoothly and accurately that is manifested in each of the following language skills:

Listening: Understanding various foods (interpersonal, ideational, textual) in various interactional oral texts and monologues, especially those in the form of descriptive, narrative, spoof/recount, procedures, reports, news items, anecdotes, expositions, explanations, discussions, comments, and reviews.

Speaking: Revealing various meanings (interpersonal, ideational, textual) in various oral and monologue interactional texts especially those in the form of descriptive, narrative, spoof/recount, procedures, reports, news items, meedo, exposition, exposition, explanation, discussion, commentary, and review.

Reading: Understanding various foods (interpersonal, ideational, textual) in various interactional written texts and monologues, especially in the form of descriptive, narrative,

spoof/recount, procedures, reports, news items, anecdotes, exposition, explanation, explanation, discussion, commentary, and review.

Writing: Expressing various meanings (interpersonal, ideational, textual) in various oral and monologue interactional texts, especially those in the form of descriptive, narrative, spoof/recount, procedure, report, news item, anecdote, exposition, explanation, explanation, discussion, commentary, and review.

The scope of English subjects that must be covered in teaching materials includes:

1. Competence in language action that is manifested in the mastery of four language skills, namely listening (speaking), speaking (speaking), reading (reading), and writing (writing).
2. Linguistic competence (language) which is manifested in the ability to apply and understand the grammatical, vocabulary, pronunciation, and spelling elements in the text correctly.
3. Socio-cultural competence that is manifested in the ability to express messages correctly and be accepted according to the socio-cultural context associated with communication activities carried out, among others, the ability to choose formal and informal speech in communication activities by considering who is involved in communication, where communication is carried out, and in what connection the communication is carried out.
4. Strategy competence, which refers to the ability and skills to apply various strategies so that communication continues to run effectively. For example, the ability to use terms that are close to, paraphrase so that what is expressed is clearer, and use body language to clarify what is being communicated.
5. Competence of discourse refers to the ability to apply language elements, such as pronouns, conjunctions, organize texts so that they are easier to understand, and can apply the structure of conversation, such as opening conversation, changing topics in conversational activities.

Five competencies become the reference for the development of teaching materials that can be presented explicitly in learning and some are implicitly presented in the use of four language skills. In line with the applicable English subject curriculum, the order of presentation of communication competencies begins with Language Action Competencies. This shows that the focus in the curriculum is on this competency which is manifested in the four language skills that are presented more explicitly in terms of the language elements that involve both the language competence and the competence of discourse formation must be presented so that students master the unsure of the language, like vocabulary, spelling, pronunciation, structure needed for them to understand the language they are learning whereas other competencies, such as sociocultural competencies, are presented implicitly. These competencies support the competence of language action which leads to the ability to understand oral and written discourse (through listening and reading) and produce oral and written discourse (through speaking and writing) suggested in the curriculum.

3. Method

3.1. Research Method

This study takes a qualitative method aimed to determine the perception of English teachers of their schools 'conduciveness to English language learners' success. The researcher tried to

describe the perceptions of English teachers while noting the best practices as outlined in the study.

Qualitative research seeks to understand the research object of teacher perceptions by observing the object, without having to match with existing theories. The existing theory does not limit the space for researchers to capture or discover the system that is being sought (generating theory). Researchers freely try to find systems or theories that exist in the object of research (Latief, 2009).

Qualitative research methods or in other terms interpretive methods (Gall, Gall, & Borg, 2003), especially phenomenology which focuses on understanding and finding meaning construction from the perspective of the subject or research participants revealed from the essence of the structure of the subject's personal experiences (Cresswel, 2009:83). The learning phenomenon studied reflects the ideas, ideas, or conceptions of the subjects regarding the conducive condition of their schools, both from the physical and psychosocial dimensions. The subjects in this study were the English language teachers at SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate.

3.2. Participants

According to Bret Hanlo & Bret Larget (Ahmad & Sukariman, 2014) Population is all individuals or units of interest; usually, no data is available for almost all individuals in a population. The population in this study was all English teachers. This research was carried out in the Senior High School 3 of Ternate because of the regularity of the university. This will help him to overcome the school regulations in researching so that teachers' perceptions about the conduciveness of their schools to ELL are the subject of this study.

3.3. Techniques of Data Collection and Data Analysis

Data collected by interview and documentation. Interviews are means of re-checking or proving the information or information obtained previously. The technique used in this research is in-depth interviews. An in-depth interview is a process of obtaining information for research purposes using the question and answer face to face between the interviewer and the informant or the person being interviewed, with or without using interview guidelines, where the interviewer and the informant are involved in a relatively long social life. Researchers create interview guidelines to facilitate researchers in dialogue or get data about teachers' perceptions of their schools' conduciveness to English language learners' success. While documentation is a recording activity to find out matters relating to the research subject.

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1. Finding

In this part, the researcher presented the table of the answer interview to make it easier for readers to distinguish perceptions of Sample A and B.

Research Question	Answer Sample A	Answer Sample B
1.	The language used by students in the learning process of English is because the students come from different regions/districts of the city	For students' use of language when learning English, it is usually returned to the classroom atmosphere. Because students come from different areas who

- and become one in the classroom as a result students are affected by their respective accents/dialect used is not standard Indonesian so that we teach students that we must adapt to the language of the students.
2. Somewhat similar to answer number one, the ability of each student also affects. Because students not only come from the city of Ternate but come from various regions/city districts. So that basic English taught from the original school has different solutions, we as teachers have to work hard and find out where the English language skills of each student are so that students in the class can understand and master the competencies that have been set according to K13.
 3. No technology supports learning English at SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate. But it is the teacher who usually takes the initiative to meet the technological demands needed when learning English. For example, when learning to listen, the teacher usually takes the initiative to bring their speaker or cellphone to play audio listening. Another example is if the teacher teaches speaking, the teacher usually assigns students to look for references on YouTube / other social media.
 4. Race does not affect learning English because of the strong culture of tolerance among school members.
 5. For economic status, it is very influential in the success of learning English because of the limited time in the K13 curriculum, in this case,
- have different dialects, of course, this influences English learning, especially in pronunciation/intonation.
- The mastery/ability of students in English language material must be different because students have different backgrounds from parents, regions, geographies, especially for students who come from the islands, of course, it can affect the ability of students to master English subject matter. Due to differences in material from the original school so that it affects the mastery/ability of students in understanding English learning in the classroom.
- In this case, technology plays an important role, but for technology that helps English lessons can be adjusted to the conditions of schools in SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate, schools are usually faced with several technological problems in schools, in this case, listening. In the process of learning listening, students are also faced with problems such as in SMA Negeri 3, Kota Ternate does not have such a language lab so students have to deal with sounds that are deliberately attempted by the teachers and fathers. The important thing is that students must also be accustomed to digesting what is conveyed in the learning process. Usually, students are also asked how to upload or download tutorials on YouTube to help the process of learning English.
- For the race, I think it does not matter because the various ethnic groups are polished in one classroom so that it does not appear that students A, students B, ethnic A, ethnic B are different.
- I think it is quite influential but not too significant because the economic status is students who are able or who have excess economic background usually

English lessons are only allocated one hour in one week, one hour is 20 minutes in duration. Even if it is two hours, the duration is only 90 minutes and that time is not sufficient to understand all the competencies specified in the K13 curriculum. Therefore, as a teacher, I suggest that students take courses outside of regular school hours. This is where the economy of the students is very influential. For those with middle to upper economic abilities, they can certainly take English courses outside, whereas if students with intermediate abilities are the opposite.

6. If for religion it does not affect it again, with the habits in SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate, tolerance is highly respected. I don't think religion affects the learning process.
7. It is influential because the culture of helping each other is so that there are groups of students in the class who are still helping each other. Influential, such as smart students only get along with smart ones. And ordinary people get along with mediocre groups. In learning English, the teacher is required to unite various kinds of backgrounds in the classroom, so it does not appear at all that in the learning process students who are smart should be on the same bench as smart ones. The point is that smart students must work together to influence students who are less able to support each other / support the learning process as smart students should be grouped with mediocre students so that the groups appear alive.
8. For the rules, policies, or school procedures at SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate are good and appropriate because of discipline and assessment. The cultural arrangement in SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate is already good, especially in English lessons. It is very influential, constrained by the time/hours of learning English because as in the previous curriculums English is allocated as much as three learning hours while for the K13 curriculum in English only 2 learning hours are allocated and this policy is very influential to students because they must be required to master many competencies in a short time. After all, only 2 hours are allocated for learning English.
9. Support from the school is good, it's just not about technology. School support is very influential because for school support the extracurricular activity process in which

- English is involved. Schools provide or facilitate students to test the abilities or competencies of each class in this case inter-class competitions such as speech contests and debate competitions are usually held and it is a form of school support for learning English.
10. The behavior of the school community is very good in the success of learning English. For example, as English teachers, sometimes we communicate using English with fellow teachers in school public spaces or in the middle of students to give feedback to the students' speak up. I think the behavior of school residents is very supportive, the behavior of school residents who support it as shown in the support given to students who take part in debate competitions between high schools at the city level of Ternate where school residents also provide support by attending events held by the government Ternate City, in this case, the education office, so I think that in SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate the school residents support each other because the competition is held outside of school hours.
11. If learning at SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate has met the competencies set in the school. The competency used according to the current curriculum is K13 regarding assessment. Everything is appropriate, for its success it can be seen from the activeness of the students participating in the English debate or speech contest. Even though they haven't entered the championship, they are confident in appearing in public. I think it is quite satisfactory for the competencies that are determined because as teachers, students are expected to be able to master the learning to completion even if some students do not meet standards, fathers, and teachers are required to invite and provide motivation and support to these students. able to master the material provided.

4.2. Discussions

4.2.1. Perceptions of Teachers in SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate

According to Sunaryo (2002:94) in Yazid & Ridwan (2017), self-perception essentially occurs because of stimuli originating from within the individual. In this case, the object is himself. Perception is a person's tendency towards something in the relative realm, meaning that individual perceptions of something will vary based on the perception of each person. Perception refers to the way sensory information is organized, interpreted, and consciously experienced. Likewise, with the object of research, the perception that arises is because of the stimulation that comes from within the individual research object through their respective senses.

The position of the human senses in the perception process, namely as a tool to interpret, therefore, the ear including the human brain is part of the coordination of the work system that supports each other so that someone can perceive something. Thus the sensing process

involves the sensory system and the brain system (the process of thinking/interpretation) which is based on human consciousness so that we can become aware of our surroundings, including ourselves. This is in line with James M Edie's (1964) Perception as the original modality of consciousness.

Likewise, the teacher's perception is the result of thinking based on his thinking ability which is motivated by various factors forming perceptions. Researchers in this case use teacher perceptions as the main data source to answer the problem formulation. Wagilto (2010) explains the existence of internal and external factors that influence a person's perception. Internal factors are factors that exist within the individual himself, such as roles, experiences, abilities, and frames of reference. Meanwhile, external factors are the stimulus itself and the environment in which the perception takes place.

Based on the explanation above, it can be seen that the process of perception occurs in three stages, namely the natural, physiological, and psychological processes. In the natural process, an object will send stimulants in the form of information that will be captured by the human senses and receptors. Then in the next process, namely in the physiological process, not all of the incoming information is recorded, but there are efforts to select which ones are the main concern. The information obtained is added or subtracted by what is known and believed from the beginning which is incomplete so that the process is more active and creative. The results of addition and subtraction produce more orderly meanings so that an individual's interpretation stage is reached.

When interpretation occurs, an understanding of the meaning of the information presented is obtained. Even though what has arrived is not necessarily the same as what has been received, it is the result of perception, it is personal between individuals and other individuals, as mentioned, is influenced by internal and external factors and is limited by the ability of the individual concerned. Perception can be expressed because feelings, thinking abilities, individual experiences are not the same, so in perceiving a stimulus, the results of perceptions may differ between individuals and other individuals Wagilto (2010).

4.2.2. Creation of School Conduciveness in SMA Negerti 3 Kota Ternate

Nasution (2003:119-120) suggests an overview of the classroom climate. The learning process should be able to create a classroom atmosphere or a classroom climate that is conducive to creating a quality learning process.

An important school learning process is not only the material being taught or whoever teaches it, but how the material is taught. How the teacher creates a classroom climate in the learning process. Many factors need to be considered in creating a quality and conducive classroom climate to improve student achievement.

The learning process is a process of learning interaction between teachers and students and between students and other students. The success or failure of an interaction of the learning process is influenced by many factors, both factors from the teacher himself, students, supporting facilities, and the atmosphere of the learning interaction process. The class climate is the condition of the classroom environment for learning activities. The classroom climate is an atmosphere characterized by a pattern of interaction or communication between teacher-student, student-teacher, and student. The class climate is the condition of the classroom environment for learning activities. The classroom climate is an atmosphere characterized by patterns of interaction or communication between teacher-student, student-teacher, and student.

4.2.3. *Measuring the success of learning English in SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate*

In essence, language including English is a tool for communicating among citizens. Communication means expressing information, thoughts, and feelings. Communication activities are manifested in the act of understanding and expressing nuances of meaning both through oral and written media which are influenced by, among others, the situation, the people involved in the communication, the topic, and the psychological condition of the people involved in the communication, through language as the main means of communication, mainly through English as a global language.

5. Conclusion and Suggestion

Base on the results of research An analysis of teachers 'perceptions of their schools' conduciveness to English language learners' success at SMA Negeri 3 Kota Ternate. It can be included that according to the data found by researchers several things make the school a little less conducive to ELL students' success, namely:

Students' abilities: Because students from various schools of different origin before, each teacher must teach English by repeating it several times so that students who lack of Basic English can adjust to each other in cells.

Lack of technology (Language Lab) to support learning English but can be handled by each teacher.

Lack of time allocation for English lessons makes students have to take courses outside of school hours. To master all competencies in the K13 curriculum and it is not evenly distributed to every student because of economic limitations.

However, some aspects seen from the teachers' perceptions are very conducive to ELL student success in SMA Negeri 3 of Ternate, it's just that schools must pay more attention to small aspects that have a good impact on ELL student success.

Based on the results of the study, it was found that several unsolved problems were found, so the researchers made suggestions. These suggestions include the following:

The success of learning, especially English lessons must be supported by all parties who have an interest in education to create a great generation.

References

- Sholah, A. (1989). *Faktor-faktor yang mempengaruhi sikap mandiri praktek mesin siswa STM Negeri prodi mesin produksi se-Kotamadya Surabaya*. Tesis tidak dipublikasikan, Jakarta: Program Pascasarjana IKIP Jakarta.
- Degeng, I. N. S., Setyosari, P., & Dwiyoogo, W. D. (2016). Strategi Guru dalam Membangun Lingkungan Belajar yang Kondusif: Studi Fenomenologi pada Kelas-kelas Sekolah Menengah Pertama di Ponorogo. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Pembelajaran*. Vol. 23, No.1, pp.10-16.
- Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia. (____). URL: <https://kbbi.kemdikbud.go.id/> di akses pada tanggal 10 oktober 2019

- Latief, M. A. (2009). *Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif*. Tesis tidak dipublikasi, Program Pasca Sarjana, Universitas Negeri Malang.
- Markus, H. R. & Kitayama, S. (1991). Culture and the Self: Implications for Cognition, emotion, and motivation. *Psychological Review*. Vol. 98, No.2, pp. 224-253.
- Merleau-Ponty, M. (1964). The Primacy of perception and its philosophical consequences in J. M. Edie (Ed. & Trans.), *The Primacy of Perception and Other Essays On Phenomenological Psychology, the Philosophy of Art, History, and Politics*. pp. 12-42. Chicago, IL: Northwestern University Press.
- Sudjana, N. (2002). *Dasar-dasar proses belajar-mengajar*. Bandung: Sinar Baru Algensindo.
- Nasution. (2003), *Berbagai pendekatan dalam proses belajar & mengajar*. Jakarta: PT. Bumi Akasara.
- Nugraha, U. (2015). Hubungan Presepsi, Sikap Dan Motivasi Belajar Terhadap Hasil Belajar Pada Mahasiswa Pendidikan Olahraga Dan Kesehatan Universitas Jambi. *Jurnal Cerdas Sifa*. Edisi 1, No. 1, pp. 1-10.
- Rahmat, P., S. (2009). Penelitian Kualitatif. *Equilibrium*. Vol. 5, No. 9, pp. 1-8.
- Ahmad, M., & Sukariman, S. (2018). The Influence of English Teacher Certification and Non-Certification towards the Students' Understanding on English Grammar at SMAN 4 Halmahera Barat and SMAN 3 Kota Ternate. *LANGUA: Journal of Linguistics, Literature, and Language Education*, 1(1), 83-97. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1443469> .
- Walgito, B. 2010. *Pengantar Psikologi Sosial*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- Walgito, B. 2010. *Pengantar Psikologi Umum*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- Winiger, J. (2015). *High School Educators' Perceptions of Their Schools' Conduciveness to English Language Learners' Success*. Electronic Theses and Dissertations. Paper 2470. <https://dc.etsu.edu/etd/2470>
- Yazid, T. P., & Ridwan. (2017). Proses Presepsi Diri Mahasiswa Dalam Berbusana Muslimah. *Jurnal Pemikiran Islam*. Vol. 41, No. 2, PP. 193-201.